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ORGANISATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR IN PRIVATE AND GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY IN KASHMIR PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

As the present changing world is facing a fierce competition all over organizations are now becoming more conscious about the positive work behaviours and even want their employees to go beyond the formal level of job description that is required to perform a job consistently (Lavelle et al, 2009). Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB), which is the work behaviour that contributes indirectly to the organization through the maintenance of the organization's social system, has increasingly aroused research interest. Notwithstanding the mounting scholarly concerns, the majority of OCB investigations have been undertaken within the Western context with very little available in India, let no unifying work is focused on the measurement of degree of change in OCB in a public and a private sector organization in particular to J&K state. Despite of existing literature on OCB, there is still lack of knowledge concerning the dimensionality and measurements of OCB in a global context, regardless of the fact that OCB may take distinct forms in different cultural settings (Farh, Earley, & Lin, 1997). In this regard, service organizations, and education sector in particular, need to be thoroughly explored because citizenship behaviours play a vital role in enhancing service quality and customer satisfaction (Bell & Menguc, 2002). Given that India's Education industry is exceptionally lacking systematic research regarding OCB, the current study aims to fill in the research gaps and add to the body of the existing literature by empirically measuring and comparing OCB among private and government school teachers.

Keywords: *Organisational citizenship behaviour, private, government.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, as educational systems has stepped into an era of reorganization and competitive and complex environment (Miller, 2002) success of schools fundamentally depends on teachers who are committed to school goals and values (Oplatka, 2006; Somech and Ron, 2007). Teacher's willingness to go ahead of the call of duty to contribute to successful change has engaged in such organizational citizenship behaviour (OCBs). It is now firmly believed that the effective functioning of an organization depends largely on employees' efforts that extend beyond formal role requirements. Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) was first used by Organ to denote organizationally beneficial behaviour of workers that was not prescribed but occurs freely to help others achieve the task at hand (Bateman and Organ, 1983). OCB is defined as "performance that supports the social and psychological environment in which task performance takes place" (Organ, 1997). The practical importance of OCBs is that they can improve organizational efficiency and effectiveness by contributing to resource transformation, innovation and adaptability which will enhance individual and organizational performance (Organ, 1988; Williams and Anderson, 1991; Borman and Motowidlo, 1993; Podsakoff and MacKenzie, 1994; Barksdale and Werner, 2001).

Sharma et. al(2011) also defined OCBs as a special type of work behaviour that are defined as individual behaviours that are beneficial to the organization and are discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system. These behaviours are rather a matter of personal choice, such that their omissions are not generally understood as punishable. Organizational Citizenship Behaviours are thought to have an important impact on the effectiveness and efficiency of work teams and organizations, therefore, contributing to the overall productivity of the organization. Organ and Ryan (1995) of Indiana University is widely credited with

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introducing OCB in academic literature. In the last three decades, it has grown to become a prominent stream of research.

Various behavioural scientists have got their own way of defining organizational citizenship behaviour. According to Organ (1988), the definition of organizational citizenship behaviour is "individual behaviour that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system, and that in the aggregate, promotes the effective functioning of the organization. Organ (1988) also noted that defining Organizational Citizenship Behaviour as behaviours that are not formally rewarded is actually too broad, as few "in-role" behaviours actually guarantee a formal reward. There is no doubt that Organizational Citizenship Behaviour is discretionary behaviour of an employee to provide "Extra" to his organization which is not a part of his defined duty. Van Dyne et al. (1995) proposed the broader construct of "extra-role behaviour" (ERB), defined as "behaviour which benefits the organization and/or is intended to benefit the organization, which is discretionary and which goes beyond existing role expectations." Thus organizational citizenship is functional, extra-role, pro-social organizational behaviours directed at individual, groups and/or an organization. These are helping behaviours not formally prescribed by the organization and for which there are no direct rewards or punishments. Organizational Citizenship Behaviour excludes those pro-social behaviours that are prescribed by the organization as performance requirements, and dysfunctional or noncompliant behaviours.

Organ (1988) has postulated the following types of organizational citizenship behaviours:

1. Altruism (Helping): selfless concern for the welfare of others. e.g., helping others who have been absent, or helping fellow workers who have very heavy workloads.
2. Courtesy: showing politeness in ones attitudes and behaviour towards other. e.g. taking steps to try to prevent problems with other workers.
3. Civic Virtue: It is a moral virtue of righteous behaviour that can be claimed to be important for the benefit of the society. e.g., attending meetings that are not mandatory, but considered important, keeping abreast of changes in the organization.
4. Conscientiousness: It is the virtue of being painstaking and perfectionist. It includes virtues like self-discipline, carefulness, thoroughness, organization, deliberation, and need for achievement. e.g., obeying company rules and regulations even when no one is watching.
5. Sportsmanship: Spirit of being positive and competitive. It involves competing with the situation and not with the people. e.g., always focusing on what's wrong with the situation, rather than the positive side.

Literature Review

Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) represents individual behaviour that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system, and that in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organization (Organ, 1988). OCB consists of informal contributions that participants can choose to make or withhold, without regards to considerations of sanctions or formal incentives. They are often described as behaviours that "go above and beyond the call of duty". The employees who perform citizenship behaviours are considered "good soldiers" (Organ, 1988) for their effort contributed without formal exchange or reward in the employment contract. Organ (1988) provided a multi-dimensional scale of OCB. The scale consists of five dimensions that make up the OCB construct which are altruism, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, courtesy and civic virtue. Paille (2009) proposed a four-dimension model of OCB consisting of interpersonal helping, individual initiative, personal industry, and loyal boosterism. Williams and Anderson (1991) found a two-dimensional structure of OCBs, and defined it as: (1) benefits directed at the organization in general, such as performing duties that are not required but which improve organizational image and performance (OCBO), and (2) benefits directed at individuals within the organization, such as altruism and interpersonal helping colleagues who have heavier workloads (OCBI).

Although most scholars agree on the multidimensionality of the OCB construct, a review of the literature reveals a lack of consensus about its dimensionality (Somech and Ron, 2007). Podsakoff et al. (2009) identified almost 30 potentially different forms of OCB and categorized them into seven dimensions based on prior conceptualizations and taxonomies of OCB (Organ, 1988, 1997; Van Dyne et al., 1994). The seven dimensions

are helping behaviour, sportsmanship, organizational loyalty, organizational compliance, individual initiative, civic virtue and self developments.

As for the educational setting, Somech and Drach-Zahavy (2000) proposed three components of teachers' OCB. The first component consists of OCB towards the school. OCB towards the school refer to behaviour beneficial to a larger and more impersonal organization. Somech and Drach-Zahavy (2000) suggest that these behaviours represent innovative and initiative activities, which are not part of the job description. The second component consists of OCB towards team member. These OCB represent behaviours intentionally directed at helping teachers in one's own team and refer to behaviour beneficial to one's own group of colleagues. The third component consists of OCB towards students. These OCB are behaviours directly and intentionally aimed at improving the quality of teaching and helping students to improve their achievements.

There has been considerable interest in the subject of OCB in business and organizational studies; however, there remains a paucity of research on OCB among school teachers (Oplatka, 2006). According to Hannam and Jimmieson (2002), OCB in teaching and other helping professions has largely been ignored. Most of the OCB literature prefers to focus on employees in more commercial settings such as hotels (Chiu and Tsai, 2006), sales (Ackfeldt and Coote, 2005), banks (Emmerik et al., 2005) and manufacturing industry (Organ & Lingl, 1995) rather than those who work in large bureaucratic systems and whose duties are often intensely interpersonal (such as teaching). Hence, this study is aimed to examine the assumed difference in organizational citizenship behaviour between government and private school teachers. Previous research that has been conducted on OCB in the education setting conceptualized this behaviour in several dimensions. The most common ones are the five dimensions (altruism, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, courtesy and civic virtue) proposed by Organ (1988) and also two dimensions of OCB (OCBO and OCBI) proposed by Williams and Anderson (1991). However, this paper will focus on five dimensions of OCB specifically for the teaching profession following A. Bakshi & K. Kumar (2009) which are conscientiousness, courtesy, sportsmanship helping co-workers and civic virtue. In general India and in particular to J&K State, much work has not been done to explore the perceived organizational citizenship behaviour difference between government and private schools. The present study clearly aims to reduce this gap of literature.

Objectives of Study

This research study intends:

- (a) To measure OCB among govt. and private school teachers.
- (b) To compare the level of OCB between government and private School teachers
- (c) To suggest on the basis of study results, measures aimed at improving OCB among school teachers

Hypothesis

There is a significant difference in the degree of organizational citizenship behaviour of employees in public sector and private sector organization.

Methodology

The universe for this study has been the teachers of govt. and private schools of district Srinagar. Data was collected through random sampling procedure. Organisational Citizenship Behaviour Scale developed by Bakshi & Kumar was used for the purpose of collecting data from the teachers. The organisational citizenship behaviour was measured on a 5-point rating scale ranging from never to always with sometimes as the middle point. The tools of analysis include mean, standard deviation & t-test.

Results & Discussions

The present study is aimed at examining the level of organisational citizenship behaviour among government and private school teachers working in Srinagar district. The data obtained on the measures of organisational citizenship is presented from Table 1.1 to 1.6, based on five dimensions of the scale developed by Bakshi & Kumar (2009). Following section focuses on these 6 tables and their statistical interpretation:

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- 1) In order to measure the degree of helping behaviour among teachers with their colleagues' two items were used to estimate this dimension of OCB. Mean scores in table 1 clearly indicates that teachers of both the schools highly engage themselves in helping behaviour and t-test finds that there is significant difference in their perception with regard to the existence of altruism in the respective schools.
- 2) Conscientiousness of an employee has been estimated through 7-items given in table 2. Mean scores on these items exhibit that teachers of both the types of schools score high on this dimension and t-test clearly indicates that there is significant difference between the two with regard to conscientiousness of the schools.
- 3) Teachers' sportsmanship has been measured through 6-items given in table 3. Mean values obtained on these items depict that teachers of both the types of schools score low on this very dimension of OCB while t-test clearly indicates that there is significant difference between the two with respect to the existence of sportsmanship among the teachers of the schools under study.
- 4) Courtesy of an employee has been estimated through 7-items given in table 4. Mean scores on these items exhibit that teachers of both the types of schools score relatively high on this dimension and t-test clearly indicates that there is significant difference between the two with regard to existence in the teachers of the schools under study.
- 5) In order to measure the incidence of civic virtue among teachers with their colleagues' four items were used to estimate this dimension of OCB. Mean scores in table 5 clearly indicates that teachers of both the schools highly engage themselves in civic virtue and t-test finds that there is significant difference in their perception with regard to the existence of civic virtue among teachers in the respective schools.
- 6) In order to estimate the incidence of overall organisational citizenship behaviour exhibited by teachers in their respective schools, five items were used to diagnose perception of school teachers. Mean scores in table 6 clearly indicates that teachers of both the schools highly engage themselves in discretionary behaviours and t-test finds that there is significant difference in their perception with regard to the exhibition of OCB among teachers in the schools under study.

Conclusion

Today successful organizations are those who have employees who are willing to go beyond their formal job responsibilities and freely give their time, effort and energy to succeed the task at hand. OCB is generally defined as discretionary behaviours that benefit the organizations and/or one's co-workers (Organ, 1988). Based on the results of the study, it is possible to state that teachers do exhibit discretionary behaviours in schools. The teachers assist new colleagues to adjust to the new work environment and help existing colleagues in their work-related matters. Moreover teachers engage in conscientiousness behaviour like obeying rules, following timely breaks, abide by the rules of the organization, reporting to duties on time, complying with the orders of the superiors. The teachers in the schools under study lack in their willingness to tolerate less than ideal situations

Finally, the teachers in these schools responsibly participate and rationally show concern about the life in the organisation. They do dispose behaviours aimed at preventing work related problems with others, assessing and doing what is best for the employees in strengthening courtesy dimensions

Despite the merits of this study, there are limitations that must be addressed. Because of our limited sample size, it may be hard to generalise the results of the study. Although the teachers sampled in our study were similar in many respects, there must be some important differences in terms of their motivational bases.

Table 1: Altruism

Statement	Govt schools		Pvt. schools		t-value
	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev	
I assist new colleagues to adjust to the work environment.	4.1071	1.06595	3.9552	1.19890	33.674
I help colleagues to solve work related problems	4.1071	0.9943	4.0597	1.02810	39.191

*significant at 1%.

Table 2: Conscientiousness

Statement	Govt schools		Pvt. schools		t-value
	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev	
I obey the rules and regulations of my organization	4.5357	.79266	4.6119	.83403	54.646
I comply with organizations rules and regulations even when nobody is watching	3.5714	1.47645	3.7463	1.50094	24.200
I fulfil the responsibilities stated in my job description	4.2500	1.04083	4.6716	.80506	49.443
I read and follow all announcements, memos and other inputs given out by the organisation	3.8214	1.02030	4.1940	.92505	41.301
I arrive early and start to work immediately.	4.1786	1.15642	4.5224	.82312	45.814
I use personal resources to aid the company(e.g., personal social connections).	2.3571	1.12922	2.5672	1.28185	19.746

*significant at 1%

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Table 3: Sportsmanship

Statement	Govt schools		Pvt. schools		t-value
	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev	
I complain about petty issues	2.3571	1.12922	1.8358	1.02391	18.008
I spend a lot of time complaining about trivial matters.	1.8571	.97046	2.0597	1.26588	16.450
I take on extra responsibilities	3.2857	1.15011	3.0448	1.37547	23.153
I complain about things which are not important (trivial).	2.1071	1.31485	2.4179	1.36125	16.817
I focus on what's wrong with the situation, rather than the positive side of it.	1.4643	.92224	1.5970	1.07393	17.371
I make a big issue out of small matters.	2.1071	1.06595	2.6716	1.50139	14.764

***significant at 1%.**

Table:4 Courtesy

Statement	Govt schools		Pvt. schools		t-value
	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev	
I prohibit behaviour harmful to my organisation	4.3214	1.09048	4.0299	1.29064	32.442
I avoid taking actions that hurt others	3.8929	1.34272	4.1493	1.30563	30.200
I keep workplace neat and clean.	4.5714	.95950	4.7761	.64716	60.025
I co-operate with my supervisor and colleagues at work	4.3929	1.03062	4.1642	1.06738	39.042
I try to avoid creating problems for colleagues.	4.1429	1.35303	4.3284	1.29554	52.776
I maintain harmonious relationships and diffuse conflicts.	4.4286	.87891	4.5672	.82064	52.636
I perform tasks that are expected of me.	4.2857	.93718	4.6119	.77763	52.637

***significant**

Table 5: Civic Virtue

Statement	Govt schools		Pvt. schools		t-value
	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev	
I take my job seriously and rarely make mistakes.	3.9286	1.33135	4.4627	1.10547	35.126
I participate in company- organised group activities.	3.5714	1.06904	3.6716	1.14664	31.706
I attend meetings that are not compulsory, but are considered important.	3.1786	1.33482	3.4776	1.18524	26.823
I find fault with what the organisation is doing.	2.5714	1.13622	2.7463	1.30666	20.922

***significant at 1%**

Table 6: Organisational Citizenship Behaviour

Statement	Govt schools		Pvt. schools		t-value
	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev	
I help my co-workers in non-work matters.	3.2143	1.13389	2.9701	1.19304	25.230
I help my colleagues in completing their task.	3.8571	1.17739	3.7761	1.07055	33.751
I engage in self-study to increase the quality of work output.	3.7500	1.26564	3.9701	1.24280	30.527
I take steps to avoid problems with other workers.	3.8929	1.16553	3.9851	1.29676	30.761
I help new workers to adapt even though it is not required for me to do so	3.6429	1.16155	3.4030	1.11545	30.005

***significant at 1%**

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